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EU-CIEMBLY

EU-CIEMBLY: Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly

5.1

EU-CIEMBLY Policy-Makers Forum (I) Report

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project number	101132694
Project acronym	EU-CIEMBLY
Project name	EU-CIEMBLY: Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly
Project website	https://www.eu-ciembly.eu/en/home

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Title	EU-CIEMBLY Policy-Makers Forum (I) Report
Deliverable	5.1
Work Package	WP 5
Leader	UC
Authors	Lucía Muñoz Benito and Dulce Lopes (UC)
Contributors	
Author's acknowledgements	
Reviewers	Fernando Borges (UC), Niall O'Connor (UE) and Isabel Valente (UC)
Type	R
Due date	30/06/2026
Submission date	30/06/2026
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
License	CCBY

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Comments
V0.1	21-05-2026	UC	First version
V0.2	12-06-2026	UC	Version after review
V0.3	22-06-2026	UC	Version after changes by authors
V1	29-06-2026	UC	Final version

How to cite this deliverable: Muñoz Benito, L. & Lopes, D. (2026). *EU-CIEMBL Y Policy-Makers Forum (I) Report*, EU-CIEMBL Y Deliverable 5.1, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.21026247.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement number 101132694. This deliverable reflects only the authors' views. The Commission is not responsible for its content or any use that may be made of the information it contains.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 5.1 provides a report on the Policy-Makers Forum organised by the EU-CIEMBLy project on 10 February 2026, at the University Foundation in Brussels. The Forum brought together members of the EU-CIEMBLy team and policy-makers at the European level to reflect on and discuss the preliminary conclusions from Work Package 2, which focuses on theorising intersectionality in citizens' assemblies, and Work Package 3, whose aim is to evaluate the effectiveness of selected citizens' assemblies through an intersectional lens. The project's main findings were presented by project's team members throughout three different roundtables which also featured the participation of policy-makers from the European Union institutions. The roundtables addressed the topics of intersectionality in public policy and legislation, intersectionality in citizens' participation, and involvement of policy-makers and other stakeholders towards intersectionality-oriented citizens' assemblies.

The exchange of ideas between the project team and policy-makers resulted in valuable feedback that is included in this report and will inform upcoming project tasks.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

I. INTRODUCTION.....	5
II. AGENDA.....	7
III. THE EU-CIEMBLY POLICY-MAKERS FORUM: OVERVIEW.....	9
1. Opening and keynote speech.....	10
2. Roundtable on engaging with intersectionality in public policy and legislation.....	12
3. Roundtable on intersectionality in citizens' participation.....	16
4. Roundtable on working together towards intersectionality-oriented citizens' assemblies.....	20
IV. CONCLUSIONS.....	24
APPENDIX 1. PARTICIPANT LIST.....	26
APPENDIX 2. SATISFACTION SURVEY TEMPLATE.....	30

I. INTRODUCTION

On 10 February 2026 in Brussels, the EU-CIEMBLY project held its first Policy-Makers Forum, which brought together members of the EU-CIEMBLY team and policy-makers at the European level to reflect on and discuss the preliminary conclusions of the project. These findings stemmed from Work Package 2, which focused on theorising intersectionality within deliberative democracy and developing the projects' analytical framework for an intersectionality-embedded citizens' assembly. And Work Package 3, which aimed to assess the effectiveness of selected citizens' assemblies through an intersectional lens, as well as to design the main features of the three pilots to be tested later in the project. The event was structured in three roundtables around the topics of intersectionality in public policy and legislation, intersectionality in citizens' participation, and involvement of policy-makers and other stakeholders towards intersectionality-oriented citizens' assemblies.

Each roundtable featured a presentation of the main project findings achieved to date, serving as a basis for structured and open dialogue among the policy-makers and other participants on key issues such as intersectionality, equality, inclusion, and deliberative democracy.

The invitation to join the Forum was accepted by representatives of various policy departments of the European Commission, the European Economic and Social Committee, the European Policy Centre as a relevant think tank for European policy and experts in stakeholder engagement from our sister project SINCRONY. There were also attendees from the European Commission services, academia and European organisations. Prior to the Forum, the participants were sent information about the project's outputs to date, including the first policy brief on Intersectionality in EU Law and Policy.

Overall, the event served as a forum to present the initial project outcomes from Work Package 2 and 3 to relevant policy-makers. It further provided an avenue for engaging with them regarding intersectionality and deliberative democracy policies within the European Union. It also offered valuable feedback that will inform upcoming project tasks.

This report provides an overview of the Policy-Makers Forum including brief summaries of the presentations. The full recording of the event is available on the [EU-CIEMBLY website](#).

II. AGENDA

The Policy-Makers Forum was held on 10 February 2026 during the morning, following this agenda:

Agenda

EU-CIEMBLY POLICY-MAKERS FORUM

10 February 2026, Brussels, University Foundation (Room Emile Francqui)

09:00-09:10	REGISTRATION
	OPENING
09:10-09:20	<p>Dulce Lopes <i>University of Coimbra Institute for Legal Research and EU-CIEMBLY Coordinator</i></p>
	KEYNOTE SPEECH
09:20-9:40	<p>Ana Carla Pereira <i>Director Equality and Non-Discrimination, Directorate General for Justice and Consumers</i></p>
	ROUNDTABLE
	Engaging with Intersectionality in Public Policy and Legislation
09:40-10:30	<p>Moderator: Dulce Lopes (<i>University of Coimbra Institute for Legal Research</i>)</p> <p>Lara Greaves <i>Victoria University of Wellington</i></p> <p>Ritu Roy <i>University of Waikato</i></p> <p>Lucía Muñoz Benito <i>University of Coimbra Institute for Legal Research</i></p> <p>Katja Reppel <i>Head of Unit D4- Democracy, Equality & Culture</i></p>

	<p style="text-align: center;">Juliane Neiiendam <i>Vice-President Permanent Group on Equality (European Economic and Social Committee)</i></p>
10:30-10:50	COFFEE BREAK
	ROUNDTABLE Intersectionality in Citizens' Participation
10:50-11:40	<p>Moderator: Giulia Sandri (<i>European Citizen Action Service</i>)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Anastasia Karatzia <i>University of Essex</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Niall O'Connor <i>University of Essex</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Ângela Guimarães <i>Head of the Competence Centre on Participatory and Deliberative Democracy (Joint Research Centre)</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Edit Lakatos and Joanna Rylko <i>Task Force Housing (Directorate-General Energy)</i></p>
	ROUNDTABLE Working Together Towards Intersectionality-Oriented Citizens' Assemblies
11:40-12:30	<p>Moderator: Lucía Muñoz Benito (<i>University of Coimbra Institute for Legal Research</i>)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Fernando Borges <i>University of Coimbra Institute for Legal Research</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Daina Naujokaitė <i>Area on Public Opinion & Citizens Engagement of the Directorate-General for Communication</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Corina Stratulat <i>Associate Director and Head of Programme European Policy Centre</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Elvira Cicognani, Ángel Honrado and Maria Aristimuño <i>SINCRONY Project</i></p>
12:30-12:50	FEEDBACK FROM POLICY-MAKERS
12:50-13:40	NETWORKING LUNCH

III. THE EU-CIEMBLY POLICY-MAKERS FORUM: OVERVIEW

The event was divided into three roundtables, aimed to stimulate debate and foster dialogue between the participants, preceded by an opening with the introduction of the project and a presentation by the keynote speaker.

Figure 1. Participants in the room, University Foundation, Brussels

Figure 2. Online participants

1. Opening and keynote speech

The introduction and welcome to the Policy-Makers Forum was given by the project coordinator, **Dulce Lopes**.

After a brief presentation of the project and the contextualisation of the event, Dulce Lopes gave the floor to the keynote speaker, **Ana Carla Pereira**, Director Equality and Non-Discrimination of the Directorate General for Justice and Consumers.

Figure 3. Ana Carla Pereira, Director Equality and Non-Discrimination, Directorate General for Justice and Consumers

In her presentation, Ana Carla Pereira highlighted the connection between research and policy making, stressing the importance of discussing how to translate analytical concepts into practical policies. The Director of Equality and Non-Discrimination elaborated on three layers of intersectionality: first, the individual level or how each person understands intersectionality; second, the conceptual level, that is, what do we mean by intersectionality and whether there is a shared understanding of intersectionality as a concept; and third, the policy level, or how this concept is translated into policies.

Ana Carla Pereira placed particular emphasis on this third layer because this is the responsibility of policy-makers, that moves from the concept to concrete policy measures. In this sense, she raised two questions regarding policymaking: on the one hand, whether policies should be broad and appeal to the majority or targeted to address specific situations, on the other hand, whether non-discrimination policies should favour the same approach for all or use forms of positive discrimination.

Ana Carla Pereira also agreed with some recommendations from the EU-CIEMBLY's first [policy brief](#), such as establishing a commonly understood definition of intersectionality across policy and legal documents and developing a toolbox for

applying intersectionality. She emphasised that further development of this toolbox, initially proposed by the EU-CIEMBLY project, would be highly beneficial.

2. Roundtable on engaging with intersectionality in public policy and legislation

The first roundtable of the morning addressed intersectionality in public policy and legislation.

It started with a presentation by **Rituparna Roy** (University of Waikato) and **Lara Greaves** (Victoria University of Wellington). As Work Package 2 leaders, they outlined the main findings of the work carried out in this work package, namely the project's conceptualisation of intersectionality, what intersectionality means for deliberative democracy and the approach taken by the project to operationalise intersectionality in citizens' assemblies across six different models. These findings can be found in [Deliverable 2.1](#), [Deliverable 2.2](#) and [Deliverable 2.3](#).

Continuing with the results of the project, **Lucía Muñoz Benito** (University of Coimbra) presented the policy scoping review of the European Union policy on intersectionality developed under [Deliverable 2.4](#). The compilation of the state of the art in legal and policy terms of intersectionality within the European Union by December 2024 was presented, highlighting the shortcomings and gaps. The policy recommendations outlined in the EU-CIEMBLy policy on Intersectionality in EU Law and Policy, drawn from Deliverable 2.4, were also presented to the policy-makers. Lucía Muñoz pointed out that these recommendations will be further developed within Work Package 5 of the project, considering the progress made by the European Union in the field of intersectionality.

Summary of findings

Figure 1. Protected grounds and social groups

Socio-economic class	Power structures	Gender identity	sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation
	Gender expression	Residence status	
	Migrant background	Marginalised groups	
sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation			sex, race, colour, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, association with a national minority, property, birth
sex, race, colour, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, association with a national minority, property, birth			
European Convention on Human Rights		Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union	
Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union		Other Directives and Policy Documents	

Figure 2. Measures to operationalise intersectionality

Figure 5. Lucía Muñoz Benito, University of Coimbra, EU-CIEMBLy researcher

Juliane Neiiendam, Vice-President of the Permanent Group on Equality of the European Economic and Social Committee, shared the perspectives of the Committee, which acts as a representative body for Civil Society Organisations. She recognised the importance of intersectionality as a condition for policy effectiveness, social cohesion and democratic legitimacy. She argued, however, that from the point of view of the European Economic and Social Committee, intersectionality is often recognised theoretically but applied selectively and implemented inconsistently. Juliane Neiiendem brought to the table some examples regarding entrepreneurship,

such as the need to reduce barriers to inclusive entrepreneurship, whose access is shaped by gender, race, disability, social status, sexual orientation, background and place of residence, and emphasised the importance to tackle all these disadvantages simultaneously. The discrimination that these marginalised groups face in finding a job was also addressed.

The Vice-President of the Permanent Group on Equality of the European Economic and Social Committee outlined four recommendations based on the Committee's work: first, clarity, or the need to share an operational understanding of intersectionality across the European Union institutions; second, mainstreaming, that is, embed intersectionality in impact assessments, funding criteria, evaluation, and the European semester; third, practicality, that is, having practical toolkits, training, and capacity; and four, accountability should be ensured through the collection of relevant data, ongoing monitoring, and enforcement of policies related to intersectionality.

Figure 6. Juliane Neeindam, Vice-President of the Permanent Group on Equality of the European Economic and Social Committee

The roundtable concluded with the intervention of **Katja Reppel**, Head of Unit Democracy, Equality & Culture of the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (RTD), who examined intersectionality in research policy. She explained how intersectionality is included in the European Research Area Policy Agenda, from the inclusion of gender equality as a structural priority in 2020, to the

acknowledgement of inclusiveness and intersectionality as principles. Regarding funding opportunities, Katja Reppel also mentioned the growing number of calls addressing structural inequalities and participation of underrepresented groups, areas that fall within EU-CIEMBLY's scope of work. Beyond this, intersectionality is increasingly featured in some health-related research calls and in the field of civil security. The need for projects to move from the theoretical findings to the reality was emphasised, and that funding instruments work as a vehicle to this end. As Juliane Neiiendam, Katja Reppel also stressed the importance of monitoring and fully integrating the perspectives of different units within the European institutions because organisational structures sometimes create siloed thinking.

Figure 7. Katja Reppel, Head of Unit Democracy, Equality & Culture of the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation

3. Roundtable on intersectionality in citizens' participation

Following the discussion of intersectionality in public policy and legislation, the second roundtable focused on exploring intersectionality in citizen participation, thereby shifting the conversation from a general perspective to the specific context of deliberative democracy.

Anastasia Karatzia and **Niall O'Connor** (University of Essex) initiated the discussion. As Work Package 3 and Work Package 4 leaders, they presented the work done mainly under Work Package 3. Thus, they explained how the project moved from theory (Work Package 2) to practice, firstly by examining how intersectionality has been incorporated into the practice of citizens' assemblies and secondly by operationalising and testing ways in which citizens' assemblies can become more intersectionality oriented. These findings can be found in [Deliverable 3.1](#), [Deliverable 3.3](#), and [Deliverable 3.4](#).

The figure consists of three main parts: a table, a logo, and a Zoom meeting interface.

EU-CIEMBLY Framework for an Intersectionality-Oriented Citizens' Assembly			
1. Analytical and normative dimension	Intersectionality as an analytical lens informs the qualities of:		
	Equality	Inclusion	Good deliberation
2. Categorising dimension	Which are then used to inform citizens' assembly design choices , categorised according to:		
	Input choices: Governance, organisation and management; selection and recruitment of participants; topic and agenda-setting	Throughput choices: Experts and witnesses in the educative phase; facilitation; deliberation	Output choices: Influence on public decision-making processes; impact on participants
3. Operationalising dimension	Which are incorporated through one or more of the models for operationalising intersectionality in citizens' assemblies.		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model 1: Descriptive Representation; • Model 2: Discursive Representation; • Model 3: Subaltern Counterpublics; • Model 4: Power Sharing; • Model 5: Agnostic Pluralism; • Model 6: Relationality and Interdependence. 		
4. Evaluation and recommendations dimension	Which then inform the development of:		
	An Intersectionality-Oriented Citizens' Assembly		

The logo for EU-CIEMBLY (Democracy for All) is located to the right of the table. The Zoom meeting interface on the right shows a video call with participants: Coimbra, Karatzia, Anastasia, GA, C, GUILMAR..., Cristina, LB, AL, Lucia Mu..., Alice Leal, AP, Alexandr..., and Antonis ...

Figure 8. Anastasia Karatzia, University of Essex, Work Package 4 leader

Figure 9. Niall O'Connor, University of Essex, Work Package 3 leader

After the presentation by the project team of the main results within Work Package 3, it was time for **Edit Lakatos** from the Task Force Housing of the Directorate-General Energy. As the three pilots of the EU-CIEMBLY project focus on housing, it was valuable to have a representative from the Task Force Housing present. Her presentation focused on the issue of housing and what the European Union was doing about it, particularly regarding the most vulnerable groups.

Edit Lakatos also addressed the issue of compartmentalisation, which had been raised repeatedly throughout the early morning. This time to point out the establishment of the Task Force, which aims to ensure consistency between the Directorates-General of the European Commission in relation to housing policies. One of its main tasks is precisely to ensure that the most vulnerable are prioritised and to give them a voice. This is reflected in the Affordable Housing Plan, which has a specific action for the most affected, including students, homeless persons, and people experiencing poverty. Edit also mentioned that the Task Force was working closely with the Cyprus presidency of the Council of the European Union regarding housing. This served to confirm that, in Edit Lakatos' view, the project had chosen the right topic for the pilots and that the timing was correct.

Figure 10. Edit Lakatos, Task Force Housing, Directorate-General Energy

Finally, the roundtable finished with the presentation by **Ângela Guimarães**, head of the Competence Centre on Participatory and Deliberative Democracy of the Joint Research Centre. Ângela pointed out that in the work they do in the Competence Centre, they do not explicitly mention intersectionality, and this is something they will institute, although it is true that they do address other categories of vulnerability, such as in choosing the topics to deliberate, the places where citizen participation take place and the power dynamics. She highlighted the lack of attention given to citizens' preferences regarding participation in democracy as well as the lack of embeddedness of citizen participation in the broader democratic organisation, which also exacerbates certain types of exclusion.

Ângela Guimarães also emphasised that deliberative democracy inherently involves gains and losses, regardless of the approach adopted. She noted that exclusion may arise not only when individuals are not selected but also when many individuals decline the invitation to participate for various reasons. To address the issue of exclusion in participation, Ângela Guimarães suggested adopting recruitment strategies that go beyond traditional statistical pools, such as recruiting door to door or targeted recruitment through Civil Society Organisations, as explored in the

EU-CIEMBLY project. Additionally, she stressed the importance of tailored facilitation methods to accommodate different types of vulnerabilities.

Finally, Ângela Guimarães shared her particular interest in the role that civic tech could play on the issue of intersectionality in deliberative democracy.

Figure 11. Ângela Guimarães, Competence Centre on Participatory and Deliberative Democracy of the Joint Research Centre

4. Roundtable on working together towards intersectionality-oriented citizens' assemblies

The last roundtable focused on strategies for engaging with policy-makers and stakeholders, with the aim of ensuring that the project's results and insights permeate policymaking and society.

Fernando Borges (University of Coimbra), Work Package 6 leader, presented an overview of the EU-CIEMBLY project's strategy for reaching different audiences and creating meaningful impact. The project has created a [community](#) within the EU-CIEMBLY Living Lab which can be joined by policy-makers, stakeholders and

civil society so that they can have access to training, events, collaborative activities, and other resources.

Figure 12. Fernando Borges, University of Coimbra, Work Package 6 leader

Daina Naujokaitė, Unit on Public Opinion & Citizens Engagement of the Directorate-General for Communication, gave an overview of the organisation of the European Citizens' Panels. She shared some practical elements on recruitment, facilitation, accommodation and methodology used within the Panels. Thus, she mentioned the six criteria they use when recruiting (geography, age, gender, education, socioeconomic background and the opinion on the EU) and the changes they have made in the way they recruit people, following a door-to-door method currently. She also stressed the importance of making people understand from the first moment that they do not need to be experts on the topic, and just need to share their lived experiences, which is also a core element of the EU-CIEMBY facilitation methodology. In relation to this, she also emphasised the way they accommodate people's different needs (single mothers, breastfeeding mothers, people with reduced mobility or health problems) and the importance of the training for facilitators and the presence of a support officer to assist anyone who might require help.

Figure 13. Daina Naujokaitė, Area on Public Opinion & Citizens Engagement of the Directorate-General for Communication

The discussion then moved on to the topic of impact, which is another important issue that the EU-CIEMBLI project should pay attention to. **Corina Stratulat**, Associate Director and Head of Programme of the European Policy Centre explained what impact means and outlined ways to generate it among policy-makers. She mentioned that impact is built through networks, earned through consistency and a smart choice of topics. It is also realised through timing, multiple channels and through institutional understanding. She made several recommendations that the project will consider in order to reach a wider audience and transfer to the policy sphere its final results and recommendations.

Figure 14. Corina Stratulat, Associate Director and Head of Programme of the European Policy Centre

The roundtable and the Policy-Makers Forum ended with **Elvira Cicognani, Ángel Honrado and Maria Aristimuño**, members of the SINCRONY project, who were invited to present their stakeholder engagement plan. They present their plan as the main output of Work Package 7 and one of the key elements of the project. Their engagement strategy is based in three boards, the expert advisory board, the youth-led committee and the communities-of-practise board. Ángel Honrado explained that, within the SINCRONY project, stakeholders are seen as co-design partners. He also explained some of the challenges encountered regarding the long-term engagement of stakeholders and how the project has adapted to solve them.

Engagement Strategy

The implementation of the plan

- ▶ Three-board **Stakeholders' Network** (designed to balance legitimacy):
 - ▶ **Expert Advisory Board (EAB)**: scientific/policy/ethical quality and alignment
 - ▶ **Youth-led Committee (YCO)**: youth agency + live experience shaping design
 - ▶ **Communities-of-Practice Board (COMBO)**: practitioners stress-test feasibility and implementation
- ▶ **Board Liaison Team (BLT)** to connect boards (coordination + continuity) and project members

Network of interested collaborators

Stakeholder's collaborative network

Additional stakeholders mapped

BLT

SINCRONY PROJECT CONSORTIUM

We devised a **partnership agreement** as a concrete tool to understand

- expected engagement, responsibilities, benefits
- quality standards + procedures for collaboration
- how input will be used (transparency and accountability)

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union under grant agreement no 101132459. UK participants in Horizon Europe Project SINCRONY are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10099512. Switzerland participants in Horizon Europe Project SINCRONY are supported by SERI grant numbers 23.00494.

Coimbra

Elvira Cicognani

Ángel Honrado

María Pia Aristimuño

Recording and taking notes

Angel's Fathom Notetaker

GA +3

Figure 15. Elvira Cicognani, Ángel Honrado and María Aristimuño, SINCRONY Project

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The Policy-Makers Forum marked the beginning of the public activities within Work Package 5 of the project, which focuses on policy impact. The primary objective of this Work Package is to actively involve and engage policy-makers and other relevant stakeholders in the project's activities and in the process of developing final recommendations.

On this basis, this first Policy-Makers forum provided a platform for presenting the preliminary project outputs from Work Packages 2 and 3 to relevant policy-makers at a European level. It also offered an opportunity to hear from them about the development of policies on intersectionality and deliberative democracy within the European Union. The event was also intended to stimulate dialogue and discussion around these topics, which was visible in the moments of interaction between the participants following the presentations.

The event confirmed some of the analyses and conclusions reached by the project in Work Package 2 and 3. Namely, the analysis of how intersectionality is addressed within the European Union institutions and the existing gaps; the design of the participatory mechanisms giving special attention to facilitation; the diverse

possibilities to address recruitment; or the decision of choosing the housing as a topic for the pilots.

At the same time, it made it possible to identify some aspects of the project that will require greater attention, such as a clearer translation of theory into practice and a purposeful engagement of policy-makers to achieve wider impact.

And, finally, the event also served as a reflection to further explore issues of interest to policy-makers, such as the development of the toolbox to operationalise intersectionality and the presentation of concrete proposals for further embedding intersectionality into citizens' participation. Therefore, the knowledge and feedback obtained at the event will influence the future activities, tasks and final recommendations of the project.

Regarding the structure and organisation of the event, participants provided a generally positive assessment (through the satisfaction survey that was shared at the end), while also highlighting certain aspects to be improved. The main issue was the insufficient space for dialogue among participants. All the suggestions will be considered when organising the second Policy-Makers Forum, to be held around February 2027.

APPENDIX 1. PARTICIPANT LIST

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EU-CIEMBLY – POLICY-MAKERS FORUM

10.02.2026, Brussels

PARTICIPANTS LIST

No:	Full name	Signature
1	FERNAN DO VANNIR DOS S. BORGES	Fernando Van in Borges
2	NIALL O'CONNOR	
3	GIULIA SANDRI	
4	Dulce Lopes	
5 x	JACCO ANGIULI	
6 x	Serhii KASIANOV	
7 x	JULIANE NEIJENDAM	
8 x	ALEXANDRA GERARD	
9 x	Katja Reppel	
10 x	DAINA NAUJOKAITĖ	

The project is funded by the European programme Horizon Europe 2021-2027, under the topic Intersectionality and equality in deliberative and participatory democratic spaces (HORIZON-CL2-2023-DEMOCRACY-01-07) with a funding of approximately three million euros. It started on the 1st of January 2024 and will be completed at the end of 2028.

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11	✗	DARIA ARLAUI	<i>[Signature]</i>
12	✗	gheyseluck Olivia	<i>[Signature]</i>
13	x	Seneray KAYKAG	<i>[Signature]</i>
14	x	EDIT LAKATOS	<i>[Signature]</i>
15	✗	CORINA STRATULAT	<i>[Signature]</i>
16	x	ANA CARLA PEREIRA	<i>[Signature]</i>
17		LUCIA MUÑOZ BENITO	<i>[Signature]</i>
18		Jaakko Sivén.	
19		Ângela Guimarães (online)	
20		Elvira Cicognani (online)	
21		Angel Hornado (online)	
22		Maia Aristimúo (online)	
23		Anastasia Karatzias (online)	
24		Ritupoma Roy (online)	

The project is funded by the European programme Horizon Europe 2021-2027, under the topic Intersectionality and equality in deliberative and participatory democratic spaces (HORIZON-CL2-2023-DEMOCRACY-01-07) with a funding of approximately three million euros. It started on the 1st of January 2024 and will be completed at the end of 2028.

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25	Lara Freaves (online)	
26	Antonis Karatzias (online)	
27	Alice Leal (online)	
26	Cristina Pérez (online)	
29	Claire Morot (online)	
30	Alexandros Papanourides (online)	
31	Antonella Di Masso (online)	
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39		

The project is funded by the European programme Horizon Europe 2021-2027, under the topic Intersectionality and equality in deliberative and participatory democratic spaces (HORIZON-CL2-2023-DEMOCRACY-01-07) with a funding of approximately three million euros. It started on the 1st of January 2024 and will be completed at the end of 2028.

APPENDIX 2. SATISFACTION SURVEY TEMPLATE

POLICY-MAKERS FORUM

Brussels, 09.02.2026

Full name

Institution

Email address

The personal data provided in this form is confidential and it is intended only for the process to which it refers. The data will be processed by the EU-CIEMBLY Project team in compliance with the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Data will be stored securely and will not be shared with third parties outside the EU-CIEMBLY consortium without your prior consent. You have the right to access, rectify, or request the deletion of your personal data at any time. For any questions or requests regarding data protection, please contact us at eu-ciembly@ij.uc.pt

I am aware of and accept the processing of data in accordance with EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):

Yes

No

Do you authorise the recording and use of your image and voice (audio) during the event for dissemination proposes?

Yes

No

Before the event...

What are your expectations for this policy-makers forum?

What would make this event valuable for you?

After the event...

How satisfied are you with the event? (0= very dissatisfied, 5=very satisfied)

1	2	3	4	5

Did the event meet your expectations?

What could we improve for future events?

What are your key takeaways from the event?

Do you have any recommendations for the project?